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PROOF-OF-CONCEPT OXALOGENESIS- OXALOTROPHY PATHWAY FOR BIORECOVERY OF LI

Summary:

In this report we present the data supporting the feasibility of implementing a pathway combining fungal oxalogenesis and bacterial oxalotrophy for the biorecovery of Li from deep geothermal fluids. While we provide data only for Li, we also provide a theoretical background on how Sr could be targeted using the same approach. The biorecovery approach consists on the following steps: 1) Oxalic acid production by a fungal strain, 2) Fluid filtration with oxalic acid in order to remove impurities such as Ca, and 3) Li immobilization as Li-carbonates via fluid alkalization by bacterial oxalotrophy.

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In this report we present the data supporting the feasibility of implementing a pathway combining fungal oxalogenesis and bacterial oxalotrophy for the biorecovery of Li from deep geothermal fluids. While we provide data only for Li, we also provide a theoretical background on how Sr could be targeted using the same approach. The biorecovery approach consists of the following steps: 1) Oxalic acid (OA) production by a fungal strain, 2) Fluid filtration with oxalic acid in order to remove impurities such as Ca, and 3) Li immobilization as Li-carbonates via fluid alkalization by bacterial oxalotrophy.

The data obtained under laboratory condition demonstrate the feasibility of the pathway. A strain of the fungus *A. niger* was able to produce OA at concentrations that are compatible with the next step in the pathway, i.e. at least 10 g/L. Fluid cleaning with OA in order to remove Ca (and other elements) via oxalate precipitation was possible for brines containing up to 54 g Ca/L which corresponds to the high salinity synthetic brine that the project partners agreed upon as experimental test solution. Finally, while actual Li_2CO_3 precipitation was not experimentally achieved yet, a simple geochemical model indicated that given a Li concentration of at least 400 ppm, Li_2CO_3 precipitation via oxalotrophy is theoretically possible. In addition, a sequential system has been proofed in order to allow the oxalotrophic bacteria to resume growth and alkalize its medium.

As a result, in order to combine the three steps of the pathway at a pilot scale we propose to set up a sequential system. For this, further experiments will concentrate on optimizing OA production by our best OA producing strain *A. niger*, increasing Li concentration in the Ca-cleaned fluid via biosorption, and optimizing the stages of the sequential system in order to maximize Ca removal vs Li recovery as Li_2CO_3 .

2 OXALOGENESIS-OXALOTROPHY PATHWAY FOR BIORECOVERY OF LI AND SR

2.1 OXALIC ACID PRODUCTION BY FUNGAL STRAINS

The aim of this step is to optimize the production of the fungal metabolite oxalic acid (OA). For this, we tested two strains from our collection: *Aspergillus niger* NEUM8 and *Meyerozyma guilliermondi* NEUM232. *A. niger* is well known for its capacity to produce a large array of low molecular weight organic acids (LMWOA). In particular, *A. niger* NEUM8 produces a large amount of OA as compared to other LMWOA. *M. guilliermondi* NEUM232 has been isolated from a deep geothermal fluid (Bregnard et al. submitted). It is a dimorphic yeast fungus and may therefore be easier to handle in a bioreactor system. Indeed, the filamentous growth of *A. niger* can represent a problem in terms of biomass aggregation while this is less of a problem with single-celled biomass. The performance of both *A. niger* and *M. guilliermondi* in terms of growth and OA production was assessed first in batch and then in a bioreactor system in semi-continuous conditions. The latter allows exploring the behaviour of the two fungal strains in an industrial-relevant setting and optimize OA production as a function of diverse parameters, among which the input of carbon (C).

2.1.1 Batch incubations

OA and citric acid (CA) production in both strains was first assessed in flasks (batch system, 7 days incubation) as a function of the C source (quality and quantity). In addition, we tested whether incubating the strains directly in presence of an actual geothermal fluid would influence OA and CA production as the presence of Ca is expected to trigger LMWOA production. Hence, eight treatments were compared: two C sources (saccharose and glycerol), at two different concentrations (10 g/L and 30 g/L), and in presence or not of a raw geothermal fluid with 40 ppm Li provided by Cornish-Lithium (CLL). Saccharose is considered the optimal C source in terms of LMWOA production but it has a high cost (approx. USD 150/kg). It is also considered a primary food for human nutrition and thus not an ideal option for industrial cultivation. For this reason, we compared it to glycerol, a waste product of biofuel production with a lower cost (approx. USD 40/kg) and no direct use as food or humans. Therefore, in all experiments, saccharose provides a point of comparison to other microbial growth substrates by providing the highest potential for LMWOA/OA production which will then be compared to less energetic substrates such as glycerol.

OA and CA were measured using colorimetric assay kits. As expected, the condition involving *A. niger*, a high saccharose concentration, and CLL raw fluid resulted in the highest production of OA (Fig. 1A). On the other hand, the yeast *M. guilliermondi* appears to be a better CA than an OA producer (Fig. 1B). In addition to this, the two fungi appeared to have fully consumed their C source when low concentrations were used. On the contrary, with the high C source concentration we measured 20 g/L as a residual C in all conditions, indicating that in a batch system, the C source is not the limiting factor and that metabolite accumulation is likely the influential factor (Fig. 1C-D). Finally, in terms of the final pH reached during these batch experiment, overall *A. niger* led to more acidic values at pH 1.1 - 1.6, compared to *M. guilliermondi* at pH 1.8 - 2.5 (Fig. 1E).

Figure 1: Production of oxalic acid (A) and citric acid (B), remaining saccharose (C) and glycerol (D), and final pH reached (E) after incubation of *A. niger* and *M. guilliermondii* in different conditions after 7 days on a rotary shaker (120 rpm) at 30°C: L = 10 g/L, H = 30 g/L, Sac = Saccharose, Gly = Glycerol, CRM = raw geothermal fluid used instead of deionized water to prepare the incubation media. N=3.

2.1.2 *A. niger* bioreactor incubation

Based on the results obtained in batch incubations, *A. niger* was selected as preferred fungal strain for further experiments. Nevertheless, the potential of *M. guilliermondii* is also explored and the results are presented in section 2.1.3.

First, we evaluated *A. niger* using an optimized nutrient-rich medium containing saccharose and assessed biomass evolution and fungal activity via O_2 consumption, CO_2 production, and pH evolution. This was done in two consecutive batches, where biomass from the first batch was reused to inoculate the second batch, thereby allowing to evaluate the impact of biomass reuse which is another important aspect of industrial microbial cultivation. In this experiment, we were unable to monitor the biomass of this filamentous fungus in an accurate way as classical biomass monitoring methods appeared unsuitable. In addition to this, at the time of writing this report, we still do not have meaningful measurements regarding the LMWOA profile due to peak interference during UPLC analyses.

In the first batch (day 0 to 7; Fig. 2), we observed an initial pH drop from 6.3 to 3.5 after a brief lag phase within a day (day 0 to 1). This was concomitant to a decrease in dissolved O_2 and an increase in dissolved CO_2 . After this, pH stabilized for 3 days (day 1 to 3) together with a short rise in dissolved O_2 which then falls to 0% within less than a day. Conversely, CO_2 follows an inverse pattern. At day 3, the pH started decreasing further down to 1.91 over 2 days. Then pH drop continued but at a lower rate. Between day 2 and 7, dissolved

O₂ remained at 0% while dissolved CO₂ increased until day 5 to decrease again. The decrease in dissolved CO₂ corresponds to the change in slope of the pH curve.

In the second batch (day 7 to 14; Fig 2), the starting pH was 2.35. This is most probably the result of acidic exopolymeric substances (EPS) trapped within the hyphal pellets from batch 1 and used to inoculate the 2nd batch. However, one cannot exclude that the filamentous growth of *A. niger* had an influence on the accuracy of the measurements. Indeed, as indicated before, the filamentous and branched growth pattern is not optimal for bioreactor growth and most systems are not optimized for this. Between day 7 and 11, the pH remains stable but dissolved O₂ drops in two steps down to 0%. This two-step drop consists in a 1-day quick drop, then a slight increase followed by a stable phase and a final quick drop. On the other hand, dissolved CO₂ increases for 2.5 days to then decrease for 1.5 days. At day 11, dissolved CO₂ starts to increase again and this is concomitant to a slight pH decrease down to 1.77. Finally, dissolved CO₂ decrease again between day 13 and 14.

Figure 2: pH, dissolved O₂, and dissolved CO₂ evolution during the continuous cultivation of *A. niger* in two batches using biomass from batch 1 to inoculate batch 2.

Altogether, the variations in pH, along with dissolved O₂ and CO₂ indicate a complex metabolism and the production of metabolites in a successive manner. First of all, the rapid oxygen consumption suggests a high metabolic activity which seems not to affect negatively the production of LMWOA as the pH drop appeared to be stimulated. In particular, two distinct types of activity could be observed: 1) one in presence of O₂ and associated to a first pH drop and only in the first batch and 2) one without O₂ but associated to a second pH drop. At this stage, and given the results so far, biomass reuse appears to have only a minimal impact on production but this remains to be confirmed with LMWOA analyses

2.1.3 *M. guillermondi* bioreactor cultivation

M. guillermondi was evaluated using the same optimized nutrient-rich medium containing saccharose. Glycerol experiments will be performed in a second step. Biomass evolution was assessed along to fungal activity via O₂ consumption and pH evolution. Similarly to *A. niger*, the experiment was run across two consecutive batches where biomass from the first batch was reused to inoculate the second batch. In this experiment, we were unable to monitor the dissolved CO₂ concentration due to a failure of the measuring probe. In addition to this, at the time of writing this report, similarly to *A. niger*, we still do not have meaningful measurements regarding the LMWOA profile for the same reasons indicated above.

In the first batch (day 0 to 7; Fig. 3), *M. guillermondi* was inoculated using a fresh suspension at 10⁶ cells/mL (corresponding to a biomass weight in g/L under detection limit, hence set at 0 g/L). The second batch (day 7 to 14) was inoculated by using biomass filtered from the first batch and resuspended in a fresh medium. At the end of the first batch, biomass was measured at 1.8 g/L which increased to 3.5 g/L by the end of the second batch. Noteworthy, as each batch phase ended, fungal growth had reached a stationary phase demonstrating that adding fresh medium effectively increased biomass concentration. Along to fungal growth, the pH dropped from day 1 all the way to day 7. After a one-day lag, pH dropped from 6.25 to 4.4 in 2 days, ending at 3.91 at day 7. During the second batch, the pH rapidly decreased from 5.89 to 4.35 in 1.5 days, to then gradually decline down to 4.04. Here, again, the reused biomass did not affect negatively the pH drop. Finally, the pattern in dissolved O₂ appeared to be correlated to the pH decrease, indicating a constant production of metabolites in the conditions assessed in this experiment. Finally, the peak in dissolved O₂ between day 7.5 and 8.8 is due to the formation of bubbles around the probe after the change of medium linked to biomass re-inoculation between the two batches.

Figure 3: pH, dissolved O₂, and biomass evolution during the continuous cultivation of *M. guillermondi* in two batches using biomass from batch 1 to inoculate batch 2.

In conclusion, based on the results shown in figures 2 and 3, *A. niger* appears as the best candidate in terms of pH drop since pH dropped almost down to 1.5. However, the data regarding the LMWOA profile this corresponds to is still not available, as the protocol for

LMWOA assessment via HPLC is currently under progress. Nevertheless, based on the results obtained in batch incubations (section 2.1.1), the low final pH may reflect OA production. In addition to LMWOA assessment, an additional step will be to assess biomass for *A. niger* properly. As mentioned earlier, its filamentous lifestyle hinders proper biomass measurements making it difficult to correlate biomass growth to LMWOA/OA production in bioreactor systems. In order to solve this issue, further experiments in bioreactor systems will use an alternative proxy such as gene copy number via qPCR of 18S rRNA gene copies.

Finally, further experimental steps for the optimization of OA production will involve testing C sources from waste resources that are not considered Ca-rich (e.g. excluding milk whey; table 1) in order to find the optimal balance between the cost of raw resources for microbial growth versus OA production. This step is crucial as we need to achieve around 20 g of OA per L of growth medium with one of these two species in order for biogenic OA to be competitive to abiotic OA treatments (see §2.2 as well as figure 5 and table 2 for further details). Among the alternative C sources considered in table 1, priority will be given to simple compounds such as glycerol, starch and urea (individually and combined, especially for urea as it may affect pH via ureolysis). Then, depending on the results, other more complex substrates such as lignocellulosic waste materials will be assessed considering their cost, origin, and the need for a pre-treatment.

Table 1: Alternative C sources for the production of OA using *A. niger* and *M. guilliermondi*

Food factory waste	Fruit pulp
	Brewer's grains
	Glycerol (biodiesel byproduct)
	Food waste (ex : from cafeterias)
Agricultural waste (depends on local agriculture)	Starch
	Straw (Slow degradation rate? Pre-treatment?)
	Wood shavings, sawdust (Slow degradation rate? Pre-treatment?)
	Molasses (ex : sugar beet or sugar cane) (still too expensive ?)
Other	Cyanobacteria/algae (synthetic lichen)
	Urea

2.2 FLUID FILTRATION WITH OXALIC ACID

The aim of this step is to take advantage of the poor solubility of most elements in presence of oxalic acid/oxalate (Fig. 4). This is particularly relevant for Ca, as this is the primary element that will interfere with step 3 where Li_2CO_3 precipitation is the target (solubility product K_{sp} at 25°C of $\text{CaCO}_3 = 2.8 \times 10^{-9}$ and of $\text{Li}_2\text{CO}_3 = 2.5 \times 10^{-2}$). The approach is based on the fact that at pH above 4, oxalic acid turn into its conjugated base, oxalate ($\text{p}K_{a1} = 1.27$; $\text{p}K_{a2} = 4.28$). Hence, OA added to the fluid will generate the formation of precipitates containing Ca ($K_{sp} = 2.7 \times 10^{-9}$), Mg, Sr, Mn, Al. After this step, the concentration of most elements should be decreased in the fluid, while the following elements Li, Na, K, Fe, Ti, V should remain at the same concentration due to their high solubility in presence of oxalate (reviewed in Verma et al. 2019).

Figure 4: Tendency of metals to form simple oxalate compounds (considered as chemically soluble) and/or complex oxalates (considered as chemically insoluble) (Krishnamurty, & Gordon 1961).

In order to evaluate the amount of OA needed as a function of fluid's elemental concentrations, five types of fluids were treated with abiotic OA. These five fluids corresponded to the two synthetic fluids that the project partners agreed upon as experimental test solutions, a low-salinity and a high-salinity fluid, as well as three fluids provided by CLL: a raw fluid (from well GWDD_002), a DLE-treated fluid, and a concentrated brine (through reverse osmosis). The concentrations of the main elements in these three fluids is indicated in table 2.

Small amounts of a concentrated OA solution were added to each brine until the weight of precipitate did not significantly increase, indicating that all possible elements that could precipitate with oxalate had been precipitated. This experiment has been done with abiotic AO in order to test the limits of the system. In addition, the use of abiotic AO in the initial

precipitation experiments will allow us to assess potential differences with biogenic OA, such as the impact of other metabolic products present along OA (other LMWOA and/or fungal metabolites), on subsequent precipitation.

Using the low-salinity synthetic brine, 2.10 g/L of OA were needed in order to precipitate all insoluble elements (Fig. 5 and table 2). The total amount of precipitates (weight/volume) corresponded to 2.185 g/L which aligned to the predicted value. Indeed, a mass of 2.185 g calcium oxalate corresponds to 0.686 g of calcium, matching this brine's Ca concentration of 0.667 g/L (table 2).

Comparing the low-salinity synthetic brine and the raw geothermal fluid, the solubility of Li and K appeared unaffected by the addition of OA. Ca concentrations showed a gradual decrease until reaching a threshold at around 2 g/L of OA where approximately 18 ppm of Ca remained. After this point, Ca concentration continued to decline, but at a relatively slower rate. Within the raw fluid, Na also showed a slight drop in concentration around the same OA threshold as Ca, and it remained stable otherwise. In contrary, in the synthetic fluid, Na concentrations also declined initially but then gradually rose again (Fig. 6).

Figure 5: Evolution of the pH and weight of precipitates as a result of OA addition in: the DLE eluate (from CLL; top left), a concentrated brine (from CLL; top right), the low salinity synthetic brine 1 (bottom left), and the high salinity synthetic brine 2 (bottom right).

Table 2: Concentrations of Calcium, Lithium, and Strontium in the five brines treated with abiotic OA.

	Ca [g/L]	OA [g/L]	Li [g/L]	Ratio Ca/Li	Ratio OA/Li	Sr (g/L)	Ratio OA/Sr
Raw brine (CLL)	0.586	2	0.041	14.3	48.9	nd	nd
DLE Eluate (CLL)	2.313	7.3	1.28	1.8	5.7	nd	nd
Concentrated brine (CLL)	6.984	22	0.317	22.0	69.4	nd	nd
Synthetic brine 1 (low salinity)	0.667	2.1	0.04	16.7	52.5	0.012	175
Synthetic brine 2 (high salinity)	54	170	0.204	264.7	833.3	1.9	89.5

Finally, the measured amount of OA needed to precipitate one gram of Ca can be used to extrapolate the quantity of OA required to purify Li (or Sr) by considering the actual Ca content of a given brine (Table 2). The resulting OA-to-Li and OA-to-Sr ratios indicate which brines are most efficiently purified using OA to remove Ca before extracting Li or Sr (Table 2).

Figure 6: Evolution of the concentrations of Ca, K, Li and Na ions within the low salinity synthetic fluid 1 (A) and the raw fluid (B) with the addition of OA. Concentrations measured with an ICP-OES. N=3.

2.3 LI IMMOBILIZATION AS LI-CARBONATES

The aim of this step is to increase the alkalinity of the “cleaned” Li-containing fluid by using oxalotrophic bacteria. Oxalotrophy consists in the use of oxalate as a C and energy source by bacteria. The product of this metabolism is CO_2 and a local increase in pH due to the direct transformation of a strong LMWOA ($\text{OA-H}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$ $\text{pK}_{a1} = 1.27$; $\text{pK}_{a2} = 4.28$) into a weaker one (H_2CO_3 $\text{pK}_{a1} = 3.6$; $\text{pK}_{a2} = 10.32$).

In this project we selected the oxalotrophic bacterium *Pandoraea* sp. (own isolate) for its resistance to salinity and metal concentrations (Fig. 7A), its ability to grow over a wide range of pHs (4 to 10; Fig. 7B), as well as for its capacity to increase the pH from 6 to 9 within 7 days in a Li-oxalate containing medium with Li concentration set at 200 ppm Li (Fig. 8). This strain has been isolated at the laboratory of microbiology and its genome is currently being analysed (whole genome sequencing done, annotation on-going).

Figure 7: Growth curves of *Pandoraea* sp. at different metal and salinity (as NaCl) concentrations (**A**) and pHs from 4 to 10 (1 pH unit steps; **B**) over a 48-hour period. Control strand for non-inoculated conditions.

Figure 8: Changes in pH over 9 days induced by *Pandoraea* sp. in a 200 ppm Li-oxalate Schlegel medium.

In the Li-oxalate containing medium, the production of Li-containing precipitates was observed (Fig. 9). However, X-ray diffraction analysis showed that while this was a crystalline phase this was not a carbonate but a phosphate phase, as it corresponded to $\text{Li/Mg}(\text{NH}_4)(\text{PO}_4)$ with only low amounts of Li (Fig. 10). This results from two points: first, the growth medium contains P as a nutrient for bacteria, hence it should either be provided in a non-soluble form or at lower levels. Second, Li concentration was probably

too low as compared to other elements likely to precipitate with an anionic counterpart. To investigate this part, we carried out a geochemical modelling of the system via the construction of Eh-pH diagrams. Using two levels of Li and C species, it indicated that the formation of Li_2CO_3 is not possible with Li concentrations of 40 ppm as in the CLL raw brine. In fact, in order to favour Li_2CO_3 precipitation, a ten-fold concentration of Li (i.e. at least 400 ppm), a pH above 10, and an Eh above 0 volts are required. In addition, a higher Li concentration could decrease the minimal pH required to favour Li_2CO_3 precipitation (Fig. 11). Finally, the concentration of carbon, in particular OA, influences only slightly the system. Hence, in order for this step to work in an optimal way an additional step need to be considered in order to concentrate Li from the clean fluid, either via a physicochemical process or via biosorption in order to favour Li_2CO_3 precipitation instead of $\text{Li}_x(\text{PO}_4)_x$.

Figure 9: Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) images showing the morphologies of the precipitated phases retrieved from the 200 ppm Li-oxalate Schlegel media inoculated with *Pandoraea* sp. **A-D** images come from one culture replicate, while **E-F** images come from a second one.

Figure 10: X-Ray Difrraction (XRD) pattern of a subsample of the precipitated phases pictured in Fig. 9. The matching phase correspond to $\text{Mg}(\text{NH}_4)(\text{PO}_4)$.

Figure 11: Eh-pH diagrams at 25°C and 1 atm of Li-Ca-C systems constructed with software HSC chemistry at Li concentration 40 ppm (A) and 400 ppm (B).

Another issue that was identified in these experiments, was that the OA cleaned fluid from step 2 had a pH that prevented the growth of *Pandoraea* sp. Indeed, while this bacterium is able to grow over a very wide range of pH, the minimal pH to resume growth was 4. As a result, a sequential system was tested to prevent the pH from dropping below this threshold (Fig. 12).

Figure 12: Sequential system designed to prevent a pH drop below 4 and combining OA fluid cleaning (stage 1) to fluid alkalization via oxalotrophy (stage 2). In stage 3, the remaining Ca amount after stage 2 is used as an indicator of whether the process can be diverted to Li concentration (low Ca concentration) or to an additional step of OA fluid cleaning (i.e. back to stage 1).

pH changes were monitored with a non-invasive optode system throughout the 15 days that the experiment lasted. The experimental scheme consisted in adding a definite amount of OA (comparing both abiotic OA and OA produced by *A. niger*) in order to drop the pH near 4.5 and precipitate part of the Ca (stage 1). Then, after 2 days, the oxalotrophic bacterium *Pandoraea* sp. was added to the system to trigger medium alkalization via oxalotrophy (stage 2). On the next day, if the pH had reached at least 5, more OA was added and the appearance of Ca-containing precipitates recorded. In the condition containing *Pandoraea* sp. with abiotic OA, the pH initially dropped to 4.25, before going slightly up (4.35) and stabilizing at this value after 4 days. As the threshold of pH 5 was not reached, no additional OA was added to this treatment. In the second condition, glucose was added along abiotic OA in order to prime oxalotrophic bacteria with a substrate that is easy to consume and available at lab scale. If this appears as a necessary step, alternative substrates with a lower economic value will be tested. This allowed the pH to rise higher (4.68), but it still stayed under pH 5. Finally, in the condition consisting in adding LMWOA, among which OA, produced by *A. niger*, the pH could increase again after each OA/LMWOA addition. As already indicated, OA was applied in varying amount, in order to drop the pH around 4.5: the first OA addition was 70 μ L, second 100 μ L, third 110 μ L, and fourth 80 μ L. This indicated that the oxalotrophic bacteria were able to thrive on the biogenic OA/LMWOA and had an impact on the medium buffering effect (Fig. 13). Hence, this indicates that the application of a sequential system will be required for pilot testing.

Figure 13: Changes of pH over 15 days in the sequential system described in Fig. 12. The letter A on the X-axis corresponds to the addition of OA. Changes of pH were monitored using a non-invasive optode system. n=3.

3 Conclusion

The data obtained so far demonstrate the feasibility of the suggested pathway at the laboratory scale. The fungal strain *A. niger* is amenable to OA production reaching the minimal required value of 2 g/L of OA (corresponding to the low salinity synthetic brine) and there is a clear scope in increasing this amount. Since *A. niger* is a fungus already widely used at industrial scale for citric acid production, translating this for OA production is realistic. Calcium (and other elements) removal via oxalate precipitation is possible for brines containing up to 54 g Ca/L (corresponding to the high salinity synthetic brine). Finally, given Li concentrations of at least 400 ppm (achievable with a pre-treatment of low salinity brines with a reverse osmosis technique or instance), Li_2CO_3 precipitation via oxalotrophy is possible. However, in order to combine the three steps at a pilot scale, further experimental steps will concentrate on adapting the process to the use of economically viable substrates other than saccharose or glucose, optimizing OA production by *A. niger*, increasing Li concentration and purity in the cleaned fluid (i.e. after Ca removal via OA addition) via biosorption, and optimizing the stages of the sequential system in order to maximize Ca removal vs Li recovery as Li_2CO_3 .

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